

Preparation of photosensitive WO_3 sol, its use in photocatalysis, photogalvanic cell and feasibility of fuel cell at room temperature^ψ

Sarbari Deb and S. Aditya*

Department of Chemical Technology, Calcutta University, 92, A. P. C. Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

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The photocatalytic properties of WO_3 sol has been studied. The preparation of photosensitive WO_3 sol that retains its activity for a longer period has been reported. Some studies on photogalvanic cells using WO_3 sol and oxidisable substrate have been made. The feasibility of photo-initiated fuel cell has been discussed.

Over the last thirty years researches in the area of solar energy conversion/utilisation have been given high priority all over the world and still being continued with greater effort, because of depletion in our conventional energy reserves. Photocatalysis is one of the many fields that promises for solar energy conversion. Ghosh and co-workers¹ reported the photocatalytic properties of tungsten oxide sols. According to Wasiliewa and Sinzova², when a colloidal solution of tungstic acid containing an organic reducing agent, e.g. alcohols or aldehydes, is exposed to sunlight it becomes blue due to the conversion of W(+VI) to W(+V). The reverse change i.e. W(+V) to W(+VI) occurs in the dark. Tungstic acid sol is photosensitive when freshly prepared, it loses this photosensitive property on ageing. Rustamov *et al.*³ reported on the photocatalytic hydrogen generation from aqueous organic solution using polytungstate. They used freshly prepared polytungstate by acidifying sodium tungstate. They also observed the loss of photosensitivity with time. It has been suggested that colloidal tungstic acid exists in two modifications. The variety sensitive to the action of light is assumed to get converted into the other through absorption of water.

In this paper we report the preparation of photosensitive WO_3 sol which keeps its photosensitivity for a longer period and some studies on photogalvanic cells using WO_3 solution and oxidisable substrates.

Experimental

Materials :

Na_2WO_4 (B.D.H.), H_2PtCl_4 (Johnson Mathey and Co. Ltd.), PdCl_2 (Johnson Mathey and Co. Ltd.), NaBH_4 (E. Merck) were used. All other reagents were of analytical grade and were used as supplied without further purification.

All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water and deoxygenated by bubbling nitrogen for at least half an hour as and when required.

Preparation of tungstic acid sols :

The colloidal solution of tungstic acid was prepared by mixing 100 ml of $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ Na}_2\text{WO}_4$ and 100 ml of $0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HCl}$. The mixture was kept overnight and then dialysed it to get the sol.

In another method 100 ml of Na_2WO_4 solution of various concentrations were passed through a cation exchange column (column height 12 cm, diameter 2 cm, weight of the cation exchange resin IR 120 is 30 g). The eluent was collected in a beaker containing 3 ml of the same tungstate solution, with continuous stirring using a magnetic stirrer. In some cases, the beaker containing the tungstate solution, also contained 2 ml of agar-agar solution of different concentrations plus 5 ml of 3% ammonium chloride to get more stable sol.

Preparation of colloidal Pt and colloidal Pd :

Colloidal platinum and colloidal palladium were prepared from $10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{PtCl}_4$ and PdCl_2 solutions respectively by chemical reduction by gradual addition of freshly prepared NaBH_4 solution with continuous stirring until it turned grey-brown.

Photocatalysis experiment :

For hydrogen generation the sol (containing organic compounds and/or colloidal Pt, colloidal Pd etc.) was taken in a volumetric or conical flask with arrangement to collect the liberated gas used in our earlier work from this laboratory⁴. The solution was deoxygenated by bubbling pure nitrogen for half an hour and then illuminated with high pressure mercury lamp (Phillips).

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

Photogalvanic experiment :

An U-shaped tube, the two arms of which are separated using sintered glass disc was used for the construction of photogalvanic cell⁵. The cell are filled with the tungstic acid sol and deoxygenated bubbling nitrogen through both the arms of the cell and stoppered with rubber cork. Through the rubber stoppers platinum electrode was introduced in each of the compartments. The two electrodes in the external circuit were connected to a digital multimeter [HIL 2665-Hindustan Instruments Ltd.].

The electrode in the illuminated chamber was kept perpendicular to the light path. A 125 W Phillips HPL high pressure mercury vapour lamp was used for illumination purpose. A hypodermic needle was inserted through the stopper in the dark compartment in order to detect any hydrogen gas evolution at the cathode.

Results and discussion*Photocatalysis experiment :*

The sol obtained through dialysis when mixed with ethanol and exposed to radiation turns blue. In dark the colour disappears immediately and the solution becomes transparent. The sol gets coagulated in a few days and loses its photosensitive behaviour after the precipitation settles down.

Table 1 shows how long the photosensitivity of the sol prepared using ion exchange resin persists. From the results in the table it is evident that both stability and duration of retention of photosensitivity of the solution increases in all cases where agar-agar and ammonium chloride were used as stabilizer. Agar-agar solution was used to increase the viscosity of the medium and also the large agar-agar molecule might offer a sheath over the particles and thus prevent the coagulation.

Table 1. Retention of photosensitivity and stability of various sols

Strength of sodium tungstate solution ^a /mol dm ⁻³	Agar-agar solution used ^b %	No. of days the solution exhibits photosensitivity	Stability (precipitate starts after day)
0.10	Nil	5	1
0.10	0.1	45	5
0.05	0.1	44	5
0.02	0.1	44	5
0.05	0.05	37	5
0.05	0.1	44	5

^a20 ml of agar-agar solution is present along with 5 ml of 3% ammonium chloride solution.

^b40 ml of sodium tungstate is used.

The retention of photosensitivity is maximum when 20 ml of 0.1% agar-agar and 5 ml of 3% NH₄Cl solution are mixed with 40 ml of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ Na₂WO₄ eluent through the resin column.

The effect of some transition metal ions on the photocatalytic oxidation of alcohols have been tested. When a drop of 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ Cu(NO₃)₂ solution was added to 40 ml of 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ tungstic acid sol (prepared by cation exchange method) in presence of alcohol it becomes blue under illumination. But the blue colour disappears immediately when the light source is cut off. This behaviour is in contrast to the behaviour of pure tungstic acid sol [without Cu(NO₃)₂]. The disappearance of blue colour in the dark may be due to the fact that Cu^{II} catalyses the back reaction. When a drop of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ ammonium heptamolybdate is added to the tungstic acid solution it becomes blue under irradiation and the blue colour of the reduced tungstate persists. But on addition of a drop of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ ammonium vanadate no photocatalytic properties of the solution is observed. All the above three solutions were kept overnight. Only in the solution containing molybdate the blue colour persists.

Hydrogen is generated photocatalytically from water-ethanol mixture using tungstic acid sol as photocatalyst. Prolonged irradiation of this solution leads to the formation of hydrogen and acetaldehyde in a stoichiometric ratio. Rustanov and co-workers³ reported that illumination of polytungstate solution containing organic compounds results in the formation of hydrogen at a measurable rate. They prepared polytungstate solution by mixing 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ Na₂WO₄, ethanol and platinum (colloid) subsequent adjustment of pH with 1 (N) H₂SO₄. We attempted to produce hydrogen electrophotocatalytically following the same prescription but the rate of hydrogen generation is not much as is reported. From a study of variation of concentrations of different constituents we obtain maximum hydrogen generation when the concentrations of tungstate, platinum (colloid) and ethanol are 7 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ and 3.4 mol dm⁻³ respectively. Irradiation of the deoxygenated acidic (pH 2) aqueous solution of polytungstate results in the formation of deep blue colour immediately accompanied by trace amount of gases. The same experiment is repeated with platinum (colloid) and palladium (colloid) taken individually as well as in a mixture along the solution. The rate of hydrogen generation in presence and absence of the catalysts used are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Rate of hydrogen generation for various photocatalysts

Catalyst used along with WO ₃ sol	Rate of hydrogen formation (ml h ⁻¹)
Nil	0.04
Pt (colloid)	0.09
Pd (colloid)	0.16
Mixture of Pt (colloid) and Pd (colloid)	0.20

The photocatalytic reaction may be represented as :

Photogalvanic experiment :

For the study of photovoltage the composition of the solution taken in the photogalvanic cell is the same which produces maximum hydrogen in the photocatalysis experiment [i.e. 7 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ tungstic acid, 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ Pt (colloid) and 3.4 mol dm⁻³ ethanol]. The experiment is also repeated using solution with platinum (colloid). The open circuit potential increases with illumination time and becomes steady after 5 h. The open circuit potential, V_{oc}, that develops in the photogalvanic cell without using platinum (colloid) catalyst is 520 mV. When the cell is short circuited with a load of 1KΩ, the current registered is 0.025 μA. The internal resistance is calculated to be around 20 KΩ. Even after the lapse of seven days the open circuit photopotential on illumination reaches a value of about 450 mV. The photopotential developed between the light and dark half cells produces a current which drops asymptotically at lower potential. At the same time the electrolyte in the dark compartment turns blue indicating a flow of electrons through the electrolytes in the dark half cell (reduction) when the source of radiation is cut off the electrolyte in the dark cell turns to its original colourless form of tung-

stic acid sol. Further illumination restores the photopotential and the cycle is repeated with no loss of activity of tungstic acid sol.

Other photogalvanic cells have also been set up with the variation of different parameters. The open circuit photopotential and short circuited photocurrents of such cell have been studied the results being summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Open circuit photopotential and closed circuit photocurrent of the photogalvanic cells

Photogalvanic cell ^a	Open circuit photopotential (mV)	Short circuit photocurrent (μA)
Without Pt (colloid) as catalyst (large resistance)		
(i) Freshly prepared	520	0.025
(ii) After 7 days	450	-
With Pt (colloid) (large resistance)	362	0.01
Without Pt (colloid) with agar-agar, platinised platinum electrode (small resistance)		
(i) Freshly prepared	644.4	0.03
(ii) After 10 days	530	-
With Pt (colloid)	408.7	0.002
Without agar-agar (small resistance)		
With polyvinyl alcohol (small resistance)	423	0.01

^aSemiconductor sols are freshly prepared unless otherwise mentioned. The platinum electrodes are bright unless mentioned otherwise.

The cell reaction can be presented as follows :

In the anode (illuminated)

Cathode (dark electrode) 2H⁺ + 2e → H₂

Fuel cell at room temperature :

The interesting feature of this electrochemical cell is that in the cell one oxidises an organic substrate to generate power using light as an initiator. Light produces excited W*(VI) species which oxidises the substrate. In other words it is a fuel cell working at room temperature.

Light initiated fuel cell was reported by us⁶ where free radical produced from anthraquinone (D) was used in

oxidising formate/methanol/ethanol to generate power. The reaction in general is represented as follows :

The anodic reaction is

and cathodic reaction

In the present work we have used tungstate. Polytungstates and molybdates are potential fields that need further study.

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